

INDIA'S 'SOFT POWER'- A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Preface

The study of Soft Power (SP) is a central theme in a changing world encapsulated in globalisation-an historical process of compression, blurring of borders, transnational ties and a shift from state to non state policies galvanized by information and communication technology and advanced transportation. In this realm nations pursue power defined as the capacity to assert influence, control and authority primarily through Hard Power (HP) supported by Soft Power (SP)-the former driven by economic, political and military might and the latter by attraction, persuasion and emulation. However, SP has been somewhat neglected and underestimated centring on developed nations and bypassing the Rising Powers-China and India.

In this context this paper centres on exploring more fully the political economy of facets of India's SP within a comparative frame. This centres on challenges in harnessing and diffusing institutional and cultural forces within and beyond the nation through state and non state institutions. This draws on aspects of historical and cultural strengths ranging from spiritual and philosophical to creative. Relevant insights are posed.

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I hope this paper may provoke some thoughts on the critical role of SP in international relations.

Abstract

The major controversy in the 21st century centres on globalisation. It is an historical process encapsulating compression, blurring of borders and transnational ties, underscored by a shift from state to non state policies and information and communication technology and advanced transportation. In this realm nations assert influence, control and authority through Hard Power (HP) stemming from economic, political and military might driven by coercion, compulsion and inducement. This is intensified through Soft Power (SP) rooted in attraction, persuasion and emulation galvanized by institutional and cultural prowess. The combination of HP and SP gives rise to Smart Power which boosts the hold of nations. The study of SP, however, has been underestimated, centring on developed nations,¹ bypassing Rising Powers (RP),² (China and India).³

In this context this paper explores more fully political economy of aspects of India's SP set in a comparative frame.⁴ This unfolds major challenges in harnessing and diffusing its institutional and cultural strengths⁵ within and beyond the nation through state and non state forces⁶ supported by 'traditional' and 'new technology'⁷ communication tools. This centres on tapping into facets of historical and contemporary capabilities-spiritual, philosophical, political, scientific, and creative-⁸ and spreading them inside and outside the nation.⁹ Insights provoke discussion on SP.

Analytics

Globalisation is the major challenge in the 21st century marked by compression, blurring of borders and transnational relations, and a shift from state to non state forces galvanised by information and communication technology and advanced transportation. This has been informed by different concepts of International Relations (IR), encompassing International Political

Economy (IPE), to explore the nature of conflict, security, and development. This spans the 'conservative' Realist school espousing the role of the state based on security, the Liberal school focussing on interdependence between nations, including security and economic exchange, and the Structural school which emphasises tensions between socio-economic groups shaping inter-state ties.

The nature of power emerges against this backdrop. This can be defined as the capacity to exercise influence, control and authority in the world primarily through Hard Power (HP) comprising political and military might spurred by coercion, compulsion and inducement. This, moreover, is being increasingly bolstered by Soft Power (SP) through attraction, persuasion and emulation stemming from institutional and cultural prowess. The critical notion is that HP is driven by force while in contrast SP, which has been somewhat underestimated, is ushered in through seduction centred on persuading others of the virtues of a nation's policies. The combination of HP and SP gives rise to Smart Power which boosts the hold of nations.

Comparative

A comparative study of SP using political economy captures relevant aspects of economics, politics, culture and history. This can enable a fuller grasp of the theme-SP of India vis-à-vis other nations-China and developed nations-US (primarily), Europe, Russia and Japan.

Developed nations

The US is the major nation which has exercised hegemony over world affairs through HP supported by SP. In this respect the nation has shown dominance over SP ranging from institutional capacity, encompassing advanced scientific research, democracy, freedom of expression and extensive media, and good commercial

practices, and diverse creative prowess.

The SP of the US has been popular in most regions, especially in western Europe, and in Asia, Africa and the Islamic world. However, aspects, such as its democratic values have faced resistance in the Islamic world, including in particular the Middle East, and in some developing regions. This embraces those facing heavy US military and economic intervention (eg. Iraq) and states in Africa with authoritarian rulers. Diffusion of US's attributes throughout the world centres on strong state (public) policies using diverse communication tools-exchange programmes, radio (Voice of America), aid (USAID and other avenues) and advanced information and communication technology. Over the post-war decade about 100,000 people participated in USA's cultural exchange programmes while VOA broadcasts in over 53 languages to an audience of over 91 million. The goal has been to enhance its image in the world though there have been fluctuations in the level and pattern of expenditure. Non state forces , too, such as Non Governmental Organizations, have supported the SP of the US. eg. The Ford Foundation, Carnegie Endowments. International institutions, alongside, such as the UN, about 25% of whose expenditure is funded by the US, have been vehicles to propagate its values.

Apart from its institutional capacities the US has harnessed its extensive creative talents to shape values-artistic endeavours from literature, films, and music to art-reflected in works of numerous writers (Tom Sawyer, Scott Fitzgerald, Ernest Hemingway, James Baldwin), playwrights (Arthur Miller, Tennessee Williams), film directors (Orson Wells, John Houston, Martin Scorsese, Woody Allen), actors (Marlon Brando, Cary Grant, Jack Lemmon, Sidney Poitier), musicians (Elvis Presley, Beach Boys, Chuck Berry), artists (Sidney Pollack) and art centres (Museum of Modern Art).

Europe, too, has used SP drawing on its political traditions

and artistic expressions in cinema, music, art, literature and art. This is evidenced in traditional and contemporary works of high quality- film directors (Ingmar Bergman, Federico Fellini, Bernardo Bertolucci), composers (Ludwig van Beethoven, Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart, Joseph Hyden, Johann Sebastian Bach, the Beetles), literature (Jane Austin, Somerset Maughum, Virginia Woolf, Kingsley Amis, Martin Amis, Franz Kafka), artists (Pablo Picasso, Henri Matisse, John Constable, William Turner, Rembrandt Van Rijn) and sculptors (Auguste Rodin and Henry Moore).

Russia, too, a close neighbour of Europe, occupies a unique place for its acclaimed extensive cultural heritage evidenced in the Cold and the Pre-Cold War era-music (Pyotr Ilyich Tchaikovsky, Dimitri Shostakovich), dance (Bolshoi Ballet), literature (Leo Tolstoy, Dmitri Dostokovich), painting (Wassily Kandinsky), and cinema (Andrei Tarkovsky).

Beyond Europe, Japan, a major developed Asian country, though somewhat isolated till the mid 19th century, is reputed for its cultural outputs. This encompasses film directors (Akira Kurosawa), classical musicians (Seiji Ozawa, conductor, Boston Symphony Orchestra), authors (Yusunari Kawabata, Haruki Murakami), and photographers (Hiroshi Sugimoto, Rinko Kawauchi). There is also admiration for the country's fashion, food, art, and popular music.

The US has wielded major hold over HP and SP. However, to continue to retain its influence it has to refrain from monopoly in guiding affairs in the context of a global and post cold war era. This has to be informed by a more interactive approach integrating beliefs and values of other nations.

Developing nations

Pursuit of SP by developing countries faces major challenges

from developed nations though its culture has much potential in evolving this force. This is exemplified by Iran (films directed by Abbas Kiarostami, Majid Majidi), writers from Latin America (Gabriel Garcia Marquez, Jorge Lius Borges) and Africa (Chinua Achebe, Wole Soyinka, Ben Okri), and from the latter musicians (South African Miriam Makeba and Ethiopian Tilahun Gessesse), and painters (Ethiopian Afewerk Tekle). This has to be studied intensively. This is beyond the scope of this paper.

The Rising Powers

Background

China and India are two major developing nations coined as 'The Rising Powers' (RP). Their growth has been accelerating fast with implications for re-shaping world affairs. They function under different socio-political systems-China a 'planned,' 'state directed,' and 'centralized democracy' run by one party and India a 'mixed' state and market economy based on 'multiparty democracy.' Both are major actors in global peace keeping.

The nations have been motivated by an urge to induce structural transformation to diversify and stimulate growth, defence and military capability , and expenditure in science and technology while tackling socio-economic strife and devising strategies to foster ties with other nations. They dominate the world's population (about 40%). Historically, they exerted major influence in the world in the 18th and the 19th century. In 1700 their share of world income was 45.7%: China accounted for 23.1% and India for 22.6%. However, this started to decline in the 20th century from 16.4% in 1913 to 8.7% in 1950 but then rose to 12.59% (average between 1985-1995) and 16.88% (between 1995-2003) and about 20% (2012). The two nations are expected to control over 40% of world GDP by 2025-30 and dominate the world economy by 2050. On trade and FDI in the world there are prospects of China and India, and in particular

the former, playing a major role. Their trade as a % of global GDP rose from 1.1% in 1990 to 3.6% in 2004. But over 2001-2008 China's exports as a % of world exports increased from 4% to 9% while India's share jumped fourfold and remained stable at 1%. In fact China's export share reached 10% in 2010. Its exports have become more complex and sophisticated than India's though the gap is narrowing. The share of FDI, too, as a % of global GDP, though modest at present, is expected to rise in the future, while FDI inflows have to be noted: five countries accounted for 44% of the total FDI inflows in 2012 with China having the largest share of 18%.

Both nations show impressive growth though they were hit, albeit to a lesser extent than developed nations, by the financial crisis of 2008 and 2011. China's record reveals an impressive annual growth rate: 9.2 % over 1989-2012. India, before 2008, had a growth rate of 8.9% but this slipped to 6.5% in 2011-12 marking a 9 year low. In recent years growth has fluctuated in both though remaining higher than that in developed nations and the overall world level. Over the last decade the average growth rate per year in China and India has been 10% and 8% respectively. However, in 2016, India was ahead of China, the former growing by 7.5% per year and the latter by 6.5% per year. In 2018-19 growth in India has been about 7 % and in China about 6.5%. Despite their growth performance they confront varying levels of poverty, inequality and corruption which inhibit human development.

In terms of the future the OECD suggests that China and India will account for 28% and 11% respectively of the output among 42 major economies by 2030 compared with 18% for the US, 12% for the Eurozone, and 4% for Japan. China has been ahead of India in terms of productivity and intensive investment over the past decades. The nations are forecast to grow 7 fold in the next 50 years. It is expected that by 2060 China's per

capita income will be 25% higher than the current US income while India's will languish at half the present US level. In terms of GDP per capita China's is just one sixth of the US but it is forecast that by 2060 it will reach 60% of the US's income level. It should also be stressed that China's reserves have been over \$ 3 trillion. At the same time it has been under pressure to revalue the Yuan on the premise that it is overvalued enabling the country to unfairly boost its exports.

The nations are striving to use their mounting income from growth to increase their defence and military budget: China spending \$ 95 billion and India \$ 32 billion though this is still far below the level of the US's \$ 700 billion. It should be reiterated that they are nuclear powers. They are keen on using their mounting economic might to reinforce their status but are inhibited by limited resources and experience and confront stiff competition from developed nations in harnessing their extensive institutional and cultural heritage. The state has a major strategic role through public policies to pursue socio-political goals within and beyond the nation. They share the aim of forging firm ties with each other and with other nations.

China

China has been developing its SP symbolized as its 'charm offensive.' This rests on its philosophies (Buddhism, Taoism, Diaoism and Confucianism), a state driven 'model' of development, scientific knowledge, and creative outputs (films, music, and literature), supported by mounting interest in other spheres (cuisine, medicine, tourism and sports).

Chinese thinking arising from its traditions captures critiques of western norms of 'individualism' and 'materialism.' In contrast traditional Chinese values claim to give priority to human beings and harmony, winning respect through virtues, and benevolent government, peace, and harmony without suppressing differences.

However, its political structure and notions of human rights have ignited intense controversy.

The Chinese state has aggressively pursued diffusion within the nation and throughout the world including in developing regions, such as Africa, spreading ideas on harmony, peace and order based on its traditions. It has significantly strengthened on the creative front. Its films have been internationally acclaimed and it has an array of literary and artistic talents exemplified by renowned films, film directors and actors, winning of Nobel Prize for literature, art exhibitions and cuisine - films such as 'Raise the Red Lantern' (1991), 'Red Sorghum' (1987), 'Farewell My Concubine' (1993), and 'Crouching Tiger, Hidden Tiger' (2000), film directors Zhang Yimou, Chen Kaige and Feng Xiaogang and actor Zhang Ziyi. Popularity of Chinese literature, too, shows translations of Chinese works, study of Chinese languages, and winning of the Nobel prize for literature by Gao Xingjian (2000). This has been buttressed by keen interest in Chinese values seen in popularity of Chinese television programmes, festivals, and language with over 30 million people studying Chinese, cuisine and medicine (acupuncture). This is underpinned by deep interest in its philosophies seen in rapid spread of Chinese Confucius institutes in the world. This exceeded 2,000 in 36 countries. It has also been sending many students to the US and Europe while students from many nations are going to China to study in institutions many of which are rated high internationally. This could nourish mutual exchange of values.

The Chinese state has been forceful in diffusing its norms through aid, exchange programmes and new technology, including plans to transform Xinhua, its official news agency, and establish global television media throughout US, Europe, Middle East and Africa to match existing channels (eg. BBC, CNN and Al Jazeera). A major goal is to propagate China's 'peaceful rise' though this has aroused controversy. In fact Chinese public bodies have been

ahead of India in forcefully promoting public diplomacy with an expenditure of US \$ 9 billion in 2009-10. This has been supported by its aid, development and disaster relief programmes. However, it is anxious and uncertain about allowing free reign to its civil society organizations which are seen as undermining the state's notions of SP. At the same time its extensive diaspora in many countries has potential of offering an alternative vision of SP. eg. China towns in London and New York and many cities in the world showcase different facets of Chinese life style. Moreover, this is buoyed by civil society groups holding critical exchanges on the nation's socio-politics.

China may be seen as a threat in terms of its growing military and economic ambitions. This could be tempered through SP.

India

India, as in the case of China, has been forcefully pursuing its HP centred on growth and building its defence and military capability. It has potential of using its SP to intensify its influence and make an impact on world peace, development and culture. This impinges on exploiting aspects of its institutional (spiritual, philosophical and political) and cultural (creative) prowess through state and non state actors within and beyond the nation supported by 'traditional' and new information and communication technologies.

India's SP has aroused optimism and pessimism. The challenge rests on drawing selectively on its extensive 'stock' of historical and contemporary institutional and in particular cultural experiences. This stems from multiple layers of beliefs, practices, and thinking-Dravidian, Aryan and Mongolian civilizations, Buddhism, Hinduism, and Islamic and Christian religions, and presence of foreign rulers, Persian, British, French, and Portugese. The nation can also draw inspiration from its diverse schools of thought rooted in its ancient Sanskrit language, spiritual leadership

of Gautama Buddha, political and non violence architects and social reformers, Mahatma Gandhi, Swami Vivekananda, and B. R Ambedkar, and champions of democracy and universal humanism exemplified by Jawaharlal Nehru (India's first Prime Minister).

An array of artists has intensified the pursuit of SP. This embraces poets, Rabindranath Tagore and Nurul Islam, novelist Salman Rushdie, musicians Ravi Shankar and Lata Mangeshkar, film directors Satyajit Ray, Mrinal Sen, and Ritwik Ghatak, and sculptors and painters like Nandalal Bose, M.F Hussain, and Ramkinkar Baij and Benode Behari Mukherjee. Popular offerings, too, are widening the impact of its SP-cousine, yoga, fashion, tourism and sports (example, cricket).

India's cultural strength has been made more robust through access to and command of English, an international language, accompanied by a vibrant publishing industry. The nation's educational institutions, moreover, including schools, colleges and universities could imbibe relevant values though the quality of its higher education has to be raised appreciably. Alas, none of the universities are listed among the top 100 in the world. At the same time its civilization reveals famous historical sites of learning. eg. Nalanda University, for example, is being revived as an international university. Students going abroad, too, could disseminate and share knowledge of Indian values.

The scope of diffusing relevant aspects of SP within and beyond the nation has to be re-examined.

Within the nation SP could usher in harmony and uplift people through 'unity in diversity.' The theme espoused by Vivekananda has to be seen in the context of a society with multi ethnic, religious, linguistic, and socio-economic divide. This calls for imbibing a fuller grasp of its thinking, values and practices, including its knowledge of science and mathematics

(eg. the nation is credited with inventing the concept of 'zero'). This requires formal and informal education through state and non state forces using 'traditional' and 'modern' information and communication technology in which it has expertise. Indeed, the state has made bold efforts to use of such tools to enhance grasp of the nation's heritage-publications, national radio and television ('Doordarshan') and the internet. This, however, has provoked controversy in terms of the nature, style and biases in portraying 'national values.'

Despite laudable goals of the state it is necessary to go beyond rhetorics and rituals to grapple with the contribution of major works and personalities. This should aim to avoid a fossilized, inward looking, exaggerated and dogmatic vision of the nation. Non state forces, too, could bolster the pursuit of SP through civil society including Non Governmental Organizations and specialized interest groups. They may complement or conflict with public policies but serve to pave the way for a more balanced understanding of the nation's heritage. Critical reflection on 'national identity' is also emerging through exposure to the SP of other nations facilitated through the internet and diverse domestic and international television channels. This is enabling access to information on world social and political thinking and life styles.

Diffusing major aspects of India's SP across the nation is essential to expand its global reach. This calls for exploiting its institutional and creative capacity and pursuing genuinely 'plural' and 'universal' norms. This should ensure that concepts, ideas and values informing its multi-dimensional historical and contemporary exposures are shared with other nations. This could aim to curb misconceptions and prejudices about the nation. As mentioned earlier the state has been dominant in pursuing such aims through public policies though it lags behind China. Indeed, the state has taken major steps to promote SP in developed and developing nations through exchange programmes

often initiated by the Indian Council for Cultural Relations, meetings and conferences, cultural functions organized by Indian embassies, such as under The Nehru Centre (London), and All India Radio to air historical and topical themes. The internet, too, through websites and social media, has emerged as a key instrument in diffusing SP. The emphasis has to be on exchange of ideas on shared human challenges-peace, democracy, and cultural pluralism. This, however, makes it essential to make accessible to the rest of the world complex spiritual beliefs and practices in a simple and meaningful form. This covers artistic works such as high quality music, poetry and novels, films, and paintings, sculpture and architecture (eg. temples of South India and palaces and forts of Rajasthan).

Dissemination of information, as stated earlier, could encompass established institutional and cultural assets such as thinkers, philosophers and artists. This is exemplified by thoughts of Gandhi, a spiritual and political leader, on peace and non violence, pursuing an international perspective and promoting ideas on democracy by Nehru, the politician, and the deep love of human values and emotions by Tagore, a poet and philosopher. Such figures have had a profound impact in moulding norms, such as peace propagated by Gandhi, being inculcated by the famous South African freedom fighter and leader Nelson Mandella and the US black rights civil and human rights activist Martin Luther King. Indeed, Gandhi's political thoughts on peace, Tagore's poetic reflections on life, portrayed in his 'Gitanjali,' for which he was awarded the Nobel Prize for literature in 1913, and Nehru's exposition on non alignment and international politics have made deep impressions in the world. The recent unveiling of a statue of Gandhi in London's Parliament Square, alongside that of Winston Churchill, who opposed granting independence to India, marks the world stature of the Indian leader.

Adaptation of spiritual ideas from aspects of Hinduism

and Buddhism, devoid of religious dogma, to make life more harmonious, are arousing interest in 'materialistic' industrialized societies. The nation's reputation, too, as 'the largest democracy in the world,' despite its weaknesses, could be explored more fully. This is witnessed in its holding of huge elections with the turnout of the highest percentage of voters in the world. In this realm discussions on democratic and political values could be ushered in by state and non state actors. This is exemplified by EU-India discussions on democracy and on peace and non violence, and those initiated by civil society groups, surfacing in academic seminars and diplomatic exchanges. At the same time many works and personalities, though familiar within India, are virtually unknown in other countries. These could be promoted more fully. eg. spiritual and political poets and composers such as Nurul Islam, who extolled the virtues of struggle and resistance, and, social reformers, such as B. R Ambedkar.

Artistic expression is a major sphere of SP which has been promoted by state and non governmental bodies. This has often been channeled through a number of venues -Indian cultural centres, collaboration between Indian and foreign musicians (eg. drummers from Mali in West Africa), exposure of classical Indian temple dances (eg. dancers from Orissa (Eastern India) performing in Addis Ababa, capital of Ethiopia), and cultural festivals in Europe and Africa to highlight the virtues of Indian arts (eg. exhibitions of paintings and history in Victoria and Albert Museum in London). This could be buttressed through cultural tourism. In this respect, Indian embassies and tourist offices are trying boldly to attract people to India and display its natural, architectural and historical sites. This is being eased through measures such as 'Visa on arrival' to encourage tourism. This has to be backed by investments in infrastructure to make the policy effective.

An art which has major potential in bolstering India's SP is

cinema. However, it has been dogged by challenges of finance, production, and distribution underscored by controversy over quality which can match international standards- the capacity to entertain, enlighten, and uplift audiences through 'real' and 'surreal' images (rooted in dreams and the unconsciousness). This calls for critical control over the process of production-story, script (screenplay) and casting (acting), photography (visual), sound and music, and editing.

Unquestionably, India is the largest producer of films in the world with exports of 1000 films a year to over 70 countries. The drive has been firmly supported by the state motivated by a desire to project an image of a nation which is united-evidenced in the notion of 'Incredible India'- while encouraging inflows of income from export of films. However, the Indian film industry accounts for a mere 5% of the global market (China accounts for 10% of the market) dominated by Hollywood.

The films have drawn inspiration from ancient epics (eg. Mahabharata, Sanskrit drama including music, dance and gestures) and traditional folk theatre. Producing films of high quality has been inhibited by obstacles in funding and distribution centred on market oriented commercial outputs. The industry has been trying to overcome this through low budget films and collaboration with other nations to widen and deepen the nature of creations.eg. "The Custody" (1993), centred on the declining role of Urdu and a Urdu poet, produced in collaboration with UK's Channel 4, directed by Ismail Merchant and embracing leading Indian actors (eg. Om Puri, Shabana Azmi and Shashi Kapoor). However, it is acknowledged that the majority of the films have been comprised of packaged popular, commercial outputs, primarily in the Hindi language, and aimed at a mass audience. They have been based on a song and dance routine-fantasy, romance, violence and idealized, predictable, and somewhat repetitive, exaggerated and simplified stories.

A critical examination of the major modes of films -Mainstream, Parallel, and New Age or new wave - is essential to highlight their strengths and limits:

Mainstream centres on mass oriented popular commercial films typified by Bollywood. It is claimed that they offer respite from ordeals of everyday life in a country with extensive poverty, inequality, unemployment, and relatively low levels of literacy. However, critics see them as 'escapist entertainment' far removed from reality. The songs and dances, however, in the films, especially the early ones in the 1950's and 1960's, have been of a high standard. The majority of the songs have been composed by poets (eg. Shailendra, Gulzar) and sung by talented artists (eg. Mohammed Rafi, Lata Mangeshkar, Mukesh Chand Mathur, Hemanta Mukherjee) while the dances have been rooted in classical and modern traditions and choreographed by similar skills. Talented actors, too, have graced the Indian screen. eg. classical ones in popular Hindi cinema (Dilip Kumar, Prithvi Raj Kapoor, and Ashok Kumar) and in regional films such as in West Bengal (Uttam Kumar, Suchitra Sen, Chhabi Biswas, and Pahari Sanyal in the past and Prosenjit Chatterjee, Paron Bandyopadhyay, Aparna Sen, and Ritwick Chakraborty in the contemporary era).

Parallel or Art is a style heavily influenced by Indian theatre and literature, and Italian neo-realism and French poetic realism, with limited impact of Hollywood. Such films were initiated in India by directors in Bengal in Eastern India -Satyajit Ray, Mrinal Sen and Ritwik Ghatak-followed by others inspired by their style. eg. Buddhadeb Dasgupta from West Bengal and Shyam Benegal from Mumbai (Bombay). The pioneering directors have been warmly appreciated and seen as 'ambassadors of Indian cinema.' Ray, for instance, is listed among the top ten directors in the world. The films have a 'timeless' quality winning admiration within and beyond India, and accolades and prizes

at major festivals including Venice, Cannes, Karlovy, Moscow, Chicago and Toronto.

New Age or New Wave comprises experimental approaches drawing on and fusing commercial and art based ones. This emerges in works of regional directors such as from West Bengal-the late Rituparno Ghosh ('Dahan'), Srijit Mukerjee ('Chotushkone'), Sandip Ray ('Feluda'), Goutam Ghose ('Shankhachil'), Aparna Sen ('36 Chowringee Lane,' 'Mr and Mrs Ayer'), Anjan Dutt ('Dutta vs Dutta') and Kaushik Ganguly ('Apur Panchali').

A major critique of the film industry is that Mainstream films, led by Bollywood (Hindi), has come to represent 'Indian cinema' overshadowing 'regional cinema' in languages including South Indian (eg. Tamil, Telegu and Malayalam), Bengali, and North and North-East Indian ones. In this respect the comments of the internationally renown film director, Shekhar Kapur, of Indian origin, capture succinctly the critique of Indian films-his film 'Elizabeth' (1998) was nominated for nine Oscars, and he directed 'Bandit Queen' (1994) which won the National Award for the Best Feature Film in Hindi and was shown at Cannes and Edinburgh film festivals. He stated emphatically that what we call regional cinema is probably the better cinema in India and stressed that "the whole media is about Bollywood stars" and that "there are some films of sheer brilliance that just keep getting ignored" (The Telegraph, Kolkata, India, 10 December 2018). He cited a malady in Indian cinema-people going more for quantity than quality. This message was reinforced by the renown Indian actor, Om Puri, who remarked that a minority of films produced in the country was of high quality and that there was much room for improvement before they could attract world audiences. He also stressed that the quality of acting in Indian films has to match that in foreign ones.

Regional films have no doubt espoused high creativity despite small domestic audiences. They have been internationally praised. This is illustrated by Oscar winning Satyajit Ray from West Bengal whose creation has been seen as a 'human document' portraying diverse emotions and crossing cultural barriers-the Apu Trilogy (comprising three films, 'Pather Panchali'(1955), 'Aparajito' (1956), and 'The World of Apu'(1959)), 'The Music Room' (1958), 'Charulata' (1964), and 'Nayak' (1966). Indeed, Ray is rated among the top world directors along with Kurosawa (Japanese) and Bergman (Swedish). Others, who fall in a similar mode, though more familiar among specialized film audiences in the west, include film directors such as Guru Dutt, Ritwik Ghatak, Mrinal Sen, Shyam Benegal, Buddhadeb Dasgupta, late Rituparno Ghosh, Adoor Gopalakrishnan, Anurag Kashyap, and Kaushik Ganguly. Guru Dutt's 'Pyasa' (1957), for instance, was rated among the top 100 films by Time magazine. The films grapple with a range of social and political tensions.eg. gender, poverty, and unemployment, caste and class, and conflicting values and beliefs.

Despite the criticisms of Indian films there are notable exceptions. This includes historical and contemporary ones often combining entertainment and art, beautifully filmed and scripted embodying enchanting music and dances-'Awaraz' (1951), 'Mother India' (1957), 'Pyasa' (1957), 'Moghul -e-Azam' (1960), 'Bhumika' (1977), 'Lagan'(2001) (nominated for Oscar), 'Monsoon Wedding' (2001) and 'Slumdog Millionaire' (2008)-produced by companies in North America and Europe-'Kahani' (2012), and 'The Lunchbox' (2013). International film festivals, moreover, have shown creative Indian films-often low budgeted regional ones. This exemplified by Cannes, Berlin, Toronto and London film festivals, and special seasons of 'high brow' films-as in London film festivals which exhibited Buddhadeb Dasgupta's 'Uttara' (2000) ('The Wrestlers' in English) and Kaushik Ganguly's 'Apar Panchchali' (2013).

There is no doubt that commercial Indian cinema has been hugely popular in the Middle East, South and South East Asia and Africa. But the majority of people in many countries are unfamiliar with Indian films, actors and actresses. There are some exceptions-Amitabh Bachchan, Shashi Kapoor and Om Puri. Shashi Kapoor acted in English language films including 'Samie and Rosie Get Laid'(1987) and 'The Deceivers' (1988) while Om Puri, mentioned earlier, became well established and acted in Hollywood's 'Wolf' (1994), 'The Ghost and the Darkness' (1996) and 'Charlie Wilson's War' (2007).He, moreover, played authentic roles in UK films which were critically appreciated.eg. 'My Son the Fanatic' (1997) and 'East is East' (1999).

Indian cinema has potential of evolving as a powerful tool to promote SP. This rests on capturing a global audience motivated by an urge to produce films of quality matching international standards. The holding of international film festivals marks an urge to pursue such a path-the Kolkata International Film Festival, the Goa International Film Festival, and regional international ones such as the Trivandrum International Film Festival. The future lies in evolving an alternative to 'Bollywood' drawing on Parallel and New Age or New Wave films encompassing 'experimental' ones fusing 'commercial' and 'art' based approaches. In this context the penetrating comments of Ritwik Ghatak, rated among the top film directors in the world by the British Film Institute (BFI), provoke critical thinking:

“ the movie camera is not merely an obstructive eavesdropper but a commentator, philosopher, historian, critic and poet, not a peep window into the lives of a group of characters but a testament narrating, recalling, rejecting, accepting, questioning, protesting, losing and winning” (Chatterji, page 68, 2004).

In literature Indian authors have encapsulated subtle nuances of Indian history and culture which could nourish SP. Many have

won international praise. This includes R.K. Narayan ('Malgudi Days'), Nobel prize winner V.S. Naipaul ('A House for Mr Biswas'), Salman Rushdie ('Midnight's Children') and Arundhati Roy ('The God of Small Things') who were Booker Prize winners, and Anita Desai ('In Custody'). Subsequently, others have made their mark such as India based Amit Chaudhuri ('A Strange and Sublime Address') and many residing abroad including Vikram Seth ('A Suitable Boy'), Amitav Ghosh ('The Shadow Lines'), Jhumpa Lahiri ('The Namesake'), and Abir Mukerjee ('A Rising Man'). However, many, including those writing in vernacular languages, are virtually unknown abroad. Their works could be made accessible to foreign readers through high quality translations into English. This can be illustrated by the author Prem Chand, who wrote primarily in Hindi and whose novel 'Godaan' (translated into English) won popular acclaim, and more recently Shankar's Bengali novel 'Chowringhee'(1962), which was made into a popular Bengali film in 1968, and translated into English winning the Vodaphone Crossword Award for best translation in 2007. Holding of major book fairs, too, such as those held in Delhi and Kolkata mirrors national and growing international interest in Indian authors. They could be venues for disseminating English and vernacular works of Indian authors.

Indian classical music and dance, moreover, have been seen widely as a source of SP. For instance, in the 1960's the sitar player Ravi Shankar, the sarod player Ali Akbar Khan, and the dancer Uday Shankar, were towering figures in inspiring western audiences. Indeed, Ravi Shankar was rated as a 'genius' in world music. He was popularized through his collaboration with the British pop group 'The Beatles.' Subsequently, others such as tabla (drum) player Zakir Hussain and sarod player Amzad Ali Khan have won international fame. But talented singers such as Lata Mangeshkar, Mohammed Rafi, Hemanta Mukerjee and Mukesh, though hugely popular in India and among the

Indian diaspora, are virtually unknown among western music lovers. This is despite the fact that singers such as Mangeshkar are credited in the Guinness Book of Records with over 30,000 songs. However, in recent years, Indian musicians, such as the Sufi singer Nusrat Fateh Ali Khan and composer A. R. Rahman, have come to occupy a place in 'world music.' They benefited much through collaboration with foreign musicians interested in fusing Indian and western styles. Indeed, their works have been played and discussed on high quality channels such as BBC Radio 3-a major reviewer of the arts.

Theatre and art, too, offer promise in stimulating India's SP. In theatre the most renowned group 'Prithvi' theatres in the 1940's was led by Prithvi Raj Kapoor. He was a highly talented actor and theatre manager. He played leading roles in films such as 'Moghul-e-Azam' mentioned earlier. Theatres (including street theatres) have flourished in many regions such as West Bengal and Maharashtra though they confront financial snags and dwindling audiences. In painting, names such as Hussain, are respected among some specialized interest groups. However, other sculptors and artists, though well reputed and highly respected in India, remain somewhat unknown in other lands- such as Ramkinkar Baij and Benode Kumar Mukherjee who were based in Shantiniketan in West Bengal, India. But interest in such artists is gradually mushrooming. eg. the display of paintings of Mukherjee alongside that of Henri Matisse at the Tate Modern in London in 2017 drew large crowds. Such creative talents need to be exposed more widely.

Non state institutions could complement the role of the state in pursuing SP. They could spread Indian cultural ideas in Europe, USA and developing regions. Diverse local interest groups, including in particular the diaspora (discussed later), have been stimulating thoughts on India. For instance, a recent programme on William Keats and Rabindranath Tagore

in London's famous Keats House (2017), portrayed similarities between the two figures in poetry and music. Book and food fairs, too, are arousing curiosity in Indian culture such as the focus on India in Book Fairs in London, and religious and cultural festivals, notably Dewali, the 'Festival of Lights,' in the UK.

Other spheres could broaden interest in Indian culture. This includes individuals and private interest groups propagating India's cuisine, yoga, and fashion.eg. the presence of an Indian restaurant on top of the Swiss mountain resort of Jungfrau illustrates the love of Indian dishes in 'heavenly locations.'

In terms of interplay with other nations, with whom India has historical, commercial and political ties, the support of the diaspora could be elicited to reinforce SP. It emerges that in South, South East and East Asia, Buddhism was ushered in from India over many centuries through monks and priests. The migration of labour, too, over the 19th century from India to Asian, African, and Caribbean countries, marked extensive movement of indentured labour and traders to meet colonial interests. From the mid-20th century onwards there was migration of skilled and unskilled groups to the Middle East. Towards the close of the period professionals, including IT experts, started moving to the US and Europe.

The diaspora has played an important role in India's economy through remittances. This increased from \$ 2.9 billion in 2002 to \$ 70 billion in 2012. This has to be seen against a backdrop of India's status as a 'Rising Power' with the state harnessing the diaspora to enhance commercial exchange and attract investment. Policies have aimed to reinforce the ties. For instance, a Ministry of Overseas Affairs was created (subsequently incorporated under the Foreign Ministry). Various schemes, too, such as PIO (Persons of Indian Origin) and OCI (Overseas Citizen of India) have been devised to forge links with the diaspora. Indeed, the

goal has gone beyond harnessing the latter's financial prowess with intensification of social and cultural exchange with Indians residing abroad. This has aimed to ease access of Non Resident Indians (NRI) to India while at the same time seeking their support in their adopted lands to reinforce exchange of cultures. This has been galvanized through conventional and new modes of technological communication.

The diaspora offers scope of drawing on a disparate group with a range of talents to support SP. It constitutes people from all regions of India (eg. Punjab, Bengal, Kerala) with different socio-economic and cultural backgrounds, and skills in many fields ranging from commerce, professions, technology, academia, media, and arts to politics. However, it has tended to relish idealized visions of its own home culture with minimal participation in that of their adopted land. But it could serve as a bridge between the homeland and the adopted land to enable fusing and enriching values from both. The Indian state may wish to resort to them to pursue its own goals but groups within the diaspora may adopt an independent approach. This may complement or conflict with implicit or explicit notions of the state and pave the way for a more diverse and compelling SP which other nations may wish to emulate.

The state, despite its limits, has ushered in measures to enhance the nation's image. This has been based on contacts with Indian business, visits of foreign dignitaries, increasing aid and development programmes, and disseminating information on India's developmental programmes. This has been motivated by an urge to inculcate a vision of a changing India. This surfaces in recent programmes to highlight the nation's development- 'Make in India,' 'Digital India,' and 'DDD,' Democracy, Demand and Demography and 'New India.' This has been publicized through the net and social media to reach global audiences. The state has also latched on to achievements of Non Resident Indians

(NRI) in spheres ranging from arts to science, sports and politics though the credit may be due to foreign influences. This may be a natural response arising from genuine national pride in the achievements of Indians abroad. But the impact of such news may be limited.

In summary, it is essential to re-think the interlocking of key aspects of SP within and beyond the nation in a comparative frame. This could enable a more balanced grasp of this force in enhancing the nation's influence in the world. The state may be able to exercise control over some facets while non state actors could play an independent, critical and complementary role. But to establish conviction in India's SP on the international front it has to be underscored by sustainable growth, meaningful improvement in the lives of people, and participatory democracy.

Insights

The role of SP in bolstering the influence of nations in the world has to be vigorously debated.

The RP can boost their influence in the world through SP. This could enable them to reinforce their HP and evolve Smart Power. Though the RP are still lagging behind developed nations in espousing SP it has potential to be developed as a major force. This has to challenge biases in the concept of SP-attraction, persuasion and emulation- based primarily on developed nations. In this respect the criteria and relevance of institutional and cultural norms using developed nations, and in particular the US, has to be re-vamped while embracing relevant attributes of the RP. This could infuse fresh ideas into SP in revamping the nature of power and pave the way for a more balanced world order. The RP could draw inspiration from their historical and contemporary exposures, and specially their creative experiences, while selectively weaving in values espoused by developed nations.

Realistically, the limits of resources and experience of the RP suggest that they will have to overcome major domestic and international economic, political and cultural hurdles. This calls for re-assessing the role of the state in mirroring the diversity of the nation and that of non-state institutions in grappling more fully with regional, sub-regional, and local socio-economic norms. Moreover, it is essential to re-think the role of SP for domestic and international audiences to maximize its use as a persuasive tool. This has to be accompanied by HP to boost growth and tackle domestic socio-economic tensions to instil confidence and belief in their SP.

Notes :

1. This refers primarily to the US along with Europe and Japan
2. The 'Rising Powers' encompass nations which have been coined as the BRICS group comprising Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa
3. Studies on SP have been based primarily on developed nations and in particular the US. This has been influenced significantly by the works of Joseph Nye, an International Relations (IR) expert. The onus is placed on the state to use its scientific, technological, political, social and creative forces which other nations may wish to emulate though there may be resistance to some facets. The rise of China and India suggests that they wish to harness their mounting economic prowess to combine HP and SP to create Smart Power which can increase their overall influence and challenge the hegemony of super- powers (eg. the US)
4. Political economy captures aspects of economics, politics, culture, and history and enables a fuller grasp of SP
5. This reveals the spread of India's 'popular' and 'high' culture through 'state' initiated and 'non state' forces-civil society, cultural groups, international institutions, and individuals.

The state may profess to reflect diverse regional and sub-regional socio-cultural values but in practice this may deviate from reality. This opens space for non state institutions to pursue such goals more closely

6. This can enhance the overall impact of SP
7. This encompasses 'traditional' and 'technological' modes, the former centring on radio, publications and cultural venues and the latter on advanced information and communication technology
8. This refers to 'resources' of SP
9. In this respect within the nation goals of 'secularism', 'harmony' and 'national pride' in the context of a diverse society and across the nation the virtues of 'plural' and 'universal' norms could be fostered

References :

Callahan,W and E. Barabantseva, editors, *China Orders the World: Normative Soft Power and Foreign Policy*, Woodrow Wilson Centre Press and Washington, The John Hopkins University Press, Baltimore, 2011

Cha, V.D, ' Power play. Origins of the US alliance system in Asia,' *International Security*, vol.34, no.3, Winter 2009/10

Chen, K, 'Three perspectives on Chinese diplomacy: government, think tanks and academia,' *Review Article*, *International Affairs*, 92:4, 2016

Deng,Y, ' The new hard realities: "Soft Power" and China in transition,' Chapter 4 in Li,M, editor, *Soft Power. China's Emerging Strategy in International Politics*, Lexington Books,Lanham,Boulder,USA, 2009

Devasundaram A.I, 'Bollywood's soft power: Branding the nation, sustaining a meta-hegemony,' *New Cinemas:Journal of Contemporary Film*, vol.14, no.1, 2016

Deng,Y and Moore, T.G, 'China views globalization:towards a

new great power politics?,' *The Washington Quarterly*, Summer 2004

Dhanapalan, B, Book review of *Communicating India's Soft Power: Buddha to Bollywood* by Daya Kishan Thussu. New York, Palgrave, Macmillan, 2013 in *Asian Journal of Communication*, 2014

Government of India, Ministry of Information and Broadcasting, Three Day India-China Film Festival, New Delhi, India, 22 December 2018

Hall, I, 'India's New Public Policy. Soft Power and the limits of government action,' *Asian Survey*, vol.52, No.6, 2012

Hymans, J.E.C, 'India's Soft Power and vulnerability,' *India Review*, vol.8, no.3, July-September, 2009

Indian Journal on World Peace, 'Commentary on India's Soft Power and history,' vol.xxv, no.3, September 2008

Lynch, T.J, 'Whither American power?,' *BJPIR*, vol.9, 2007

Mastanduno, M, 'System maker and privilege taker. US power and the international political economy,' *World Politics*, 61, no.1, January 2009

Mukherjee, R, 'The false promise of India's Soft Power,' *Geopolitics, History, and International Relations*, vol.6(1), 2014

Kennedy, P, *The Rise and Fall of the Great Powers*, Unwin Hyman, London 1988

Kumar, K.J, 'India's many popular cinemas. Theoretical perspectives,' *Journal of Creative Communications*, 6 (1&2), 2011

Lai, H, 'Introduction. The soft power concept and rising China,' in Lai, H and Y.Lai, editors, *China's Soft Power and International Relations*, Routledge, London and New York, 2012

Lai, H and Y.Lai, editors, *China's Soft Power and International Relations*, Routledge, London and New York, 2012

Lai, H, 'China's cultural diplomacy. Going for soft power,' chapter 5, Lai, H and Y.Lai, editors, *China's Soft Power and International Relations*, Routledge, London and New York, 2012

Lai, H, 'The soft power concept and a rising China,' in

Lai, H and Y.Lai, editors, *China's Soft Power and International Relations*, Routledge, London and New York, 2012

Li,M, editor, *Soft Power. China's Emerging Strategy in International Politics*, Lexington Books, Lanham,Boulder,USA, 2009

Li, M, 'Soft Power: Nurture Not Nature,' chapter 1, in Li,M, editor, *Soft Power. China's Emerging Strategy in International Politics*, Lexington Books, Lanham, Boulder,USA, 2009

Li,M, 'Soft Power in Chinese discourse: popularity and prospect,' chapter 2, Li,M, editor, *Soft Power. China's Emerging Strategy in International Politics*, Lexington Books, Lanham,Boulder,USA, 2009

Ling, L.H.M, *Beyond Soft Power: cultural power from India and China today through films*, *China Report* 53:2, 2017

Nye,J, 'Speech. China and Soft Power,' *South African Journal of International Affairs*, vol.19,no.2, August 2012

Nye, J, 'Get Smart. Combining Hard and Soft Power,' *Foreign Affairs*, July, August 2009

Nye, S, *Soft Power. The Means to Success in World Politics*, Public Affairs,New York, 2004

Nye, J, 'Soft Power and American foreign policy,' *Political Science Quarterly*, vol.119,no.2, 2004

Nye, J.S, 'Soft Power,' *Foreign Policy*,no.80, 20th Anniversary, Autumn 1990

Parida, S, *A Sense of India Through Soft Power*, D.Phil thesis, Faculty of Business and Law, University of Southampton, 2015

Roy, J, 'Myths of growth. India should move from slogans and fanfare to trade reforms,' *The Telegraph*, Kolkata, India, September 2016

Roy, S, 'Globalisation, China and the Changing world,' in *China and the Contemporary World*, edited by Tridib Chakraborti, S.Sen, H.N. Toppo and B. K. Das, Readers Service, Kolkata,India, 2014

Roy, S, *India-a 'Rising Power'-Myth and Reality*, Occasional

Paper, School of International Relations and Strategic Studies, Jadavpur University, Kolkata, India, May 2014

Roy, S, Globalisation and the 'Emerging Giants'-China and India, Occasional Paper, School of International Relations and Strategic Studies, Jadavpur University, Kolkata, India, May 2010

Roy, Globalisation, ICT and Developing Nations: Challenges in the Information Age, Sage, 2005

Scott, D, 'Soft language, soft imagery and soft power in China's diplomatic lexicon.' Chapter 3, Lai, H and Y.Lai, editors, China's Soft Power and International Relations, Routledge, London and New York, 2012

Singer, H.W and S. Roy, Economic Progress and Prospects in the Third World: Lessons of Development Experience Since 1945, Edward Elgar, UK and USA, 1993

Tharoor, S, Global Brief, 13 May, 2009

Thussu, D.K, Communicating India's Soft Power: Buddha to Bollywood by DayaKishanThussu. New York, Palgrave, Macmillan, 2013

Zhao, S, 'The prospect of China's Soft Power: How sustainable,' Chapter 13 in Li, M, editor, Soft Power. China's Emerging Strategy in International Politics, Lexington Books, Lanham, Boulder, USA, 2009

Zheng, Y and Zhang, C, 'Soft Power and Chinese soft power,' Chapter 2 in Lai, H and Y.Lai, editors, China's Soft Power and International Relations, Routledge, London and New York, 2012